

BLASTOCYSTIS 2024

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#Blastocystis24

FLASH TALKS ABSTRACT BOOK

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Talk 01 (T01)

***Blastocystis* colonization and gut microbiota composition in a rural Colombian community**

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis*, a common intestinal protozoan, has been associated with specific gut microbiota signatures. However, the extent and specific shifts in microbiota composition and structure, particularly in rural populations, remain unclear.

Methods: Microbiota structure and composition were evaluated in *Blastocystis* carriers and non-carriers from a rural Colombian community (n=99 human samples). The experimental procedures involved microscopy and molecular techniques (e.g., qPCR) for protozoa detection. *Blastocystis* subtyping and gut microbiota was characterized by Illumina sequencing of 16S and 18S rRNA genes, to profile prokaryotic and eukaryotic microbiota. The resulting sequences were analyzed using a comprehensive bioinformatic pipeline.

Results: A high prevalence of *Blastocystis* (90%) was observed, with both mono-infections and co-infections with other parasites. Subtyping revealed a diverse array of *Blastocystis* subtypes and coexistence patterns, with ST2 being the most prevalent ST. At the bacterial genus level, *Blastocystis* carriers were enriched in *Prevotella*, *Ruminococcus*, *Blautia*, *Clostridium*, and *Oscillibacter*, whereas non-carriers were enriched in *Escherichia*. Eukaryotic enrichments included *Entamoeba* and *Hanseniaspora* in carriers, and *Ancylostoma*, *Malassezia*, *Candida*, and *Saccharomyces* in non-carriers.

Conclusions: This study supports a relationship between *Blastocystis* colonization and specific gut microbiota signatures in a rural population. This study is one of the few studies to characterize prokaryotic and eukaryotic microbiota members concurrently. Intriguingly, gut microbiota in *Blastocystis*-carriers Colombians from rural populations mirrored Western Europeans, despite vastly different environments and diets. This suggests that *Blastocystis* may strongly influence gut microbiota structure. Further studies with broader populations and longitudinal designs are required to confirm this potential modulatory role.

Talk 02 (T02)

Uncovering *Blastocystis* subtype diversity in Portuguese ungulates: first insights into subtype specificity and cross-transmission patterns

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Abstract

Wild ungulate populations are expanding their geographic range across Europe, fostering interactions with domestic species and promoting the spread of infectious diseases, particularly those with zoonotic significance. Despite the increasing understanding of the faecal-oral transmitted protist *Blastocystis*, there is still a considerable gap concerning its epidemiology in free-ranging wild ungulate and possible transmission patterns with domestic hosts, especially with those sympatric domestic hosts raised in extensive grazing systems. Thus, we collected a total of 413 faecal samples from three widespread wild ungulates (wild boar, red deer, and roe deer) and domestic ungulates (cattle, goats, horses, and sheep) in Portugal to investigate *Blastocystis* occurrence and subtype (ST) diversity using PCR and next-generation amplicon sequencing. *Blastocystis* was present in 38.3% (158/413) of the total analysed samples (goats, 81.0%; sheep, 60.9%; red deer, 40.4%; wild boar, 34.3%; roe deer, 32.5%; cattle 32.2%), while none of the horse samples were *Blastocystis*-positive. Nineteen STs were identified, including ST1-ST3, ST5-ST7, ST10, ST13, ST14, ST21, ST23-ST26, ST30, ST31 and ST42-ST44. Mixed ST infections were the norm in domestic ungulates *Blastocystis*-positive samples (97.3%), while less common in the wild ungulates (39.0%). Our results demonstrate that Portuguese wild and domestic ungulates harbour a great diversity of *Blastocystis* STs, including STs with zoonotic potential, highlighting their role in the maintenance of the sylvatic-domestic cycle of this parasite and the associated public health risks. Furthermore, our data provide novel molecular evidence indicating that certain *Blastocystis* STs might exhibit distinctive host preferences.

Talk 03 (T03)

Spatial and genetic diversity of *Blastocystis* sp. in Italy: A network analysis

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Abstract

The ubiquitous protist *Blastocystis* sp. can colonize the gastrointestinal tracts of humans and non-human hosts. Due to the apparent variable host specificity in different *Blastocystis* subtypes (STs), assessments of incidence and subtype diversity in specific geographic areas are significant to better understand *Blastocystis* zoonotic potential. We reported the pattern of genetic relationship analysis among different haplotypes of *Blastocystis* STs to investigate spatial and genetic diversity of this protist in Italy.

Isolates from 55 *Blastocystis*-positive samples (Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria Policlinico Tor Vergata, detected by Allplex™ Gastrointestinal Parasite Panel Assay) were genotyped by Sanger sequencing analysis (*ssu* rDNA gene), checked in PubMLST for allele attribution, aligned, and analyzed through phylogenetic analysis. To these, all clinical sequences available from Italy were added, and a total of 107 isolates was used to perform the Minimum-Spanning network calculation through a haplotype analysis on polymorphic sites.

The 55 new isolates were assigned as follows: 9 to ST1 (16.4%), 7 to ST2 (12.7%), 11 to ST3 (20%), 26 to ST4 (47.3%) 1 to ST6 (1.8%) and 1 to ST7 (1.8%). From the alleles analysis, 8 different variants were detected: allele 4 (ST1), alleles 9 and 12 (ST2), alleles 34 and 36 (ST3), allele 42 (ST4), allele 123 (ST6) and allele 137 (ST7). Forty-six haplotypes (hp) were identified across the 107 isolates, with hp 41 (29.9%) and hp 34 (15.9%) as the most representative. No spatial segregation has been observed. The present work represents a further local contribution to the knowledge of *Blastocystis* sp. genetic diversity.

Talk 04 (T04)

Occurrence and molecular characterization of *Blastocystis* spp. in humans and dogs in Slovenia

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Abstract

The occurrence of *Blastocystis* in humans and animals varies greatly from country to country, with little information on its presence and genetic diversity in Slovenia.

To determine the occurrence of *Blastocystis* spp. in patients with diarrhoea, we analysed faecal samples from 249 patients who had been tested for gastrointestinal pathogens in January and February 2023.

To determine possible differences in the occurrence of *Blastocystis* spp. in sick and healthy populations of children, 379 DNA extracts from faecal specimens of the same number of children aged 0 to 6 years collected between October 2011 and October 2012 were analysed. Of the 397 children, 292 had diarrhoea and 87 represented a healthy control group without diarrhoea. The occurrence of *Blastocystis* spp. in dogs was determined by analysing 79 faecal samples from dogs with diarrhoea. The faecal samples were tested for the presence of *Blastocystis* spp. using Taq-man-based real-time PCR targeting the *SSU* rRNA gene, and the positive samples were sequenced using barcoding primers to determine the subtypes. Of the 249 patients with diarrhoea, 20 (8.0 %) tested positive. Subtypes were successfully determined in 11 of them (ST2-ST4). Of 397 children, nine (3.1 %) children with diarrhoea and six (6.9 %) children in the control group were positive; the difference is not statistically significant ($p=0.11$). We identified ST2-ST4 in three children with diarrhoea and ST2, ST3 and ST7 in five healthy children. *Blastocystis* spp. was detected in seven (8.9 %) samples from dogs, but the subtypes could not be determined.

Keywords: *Blastocystis*, humans, dogs, occurrence, subtypes

Talk 05 (T05)

Prevalence and roles of *Blastocystis* sp. and *Dientamoeba fragilis* in a clinical trial involving faecal microbiota transplantation in Irritable Bowel Syndrome

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* sp. and *Dientamoeba fragilis* are intestinal protists often associated with diverse and thus “healthy” gut bacteriome. Therefore, we investigated their prevalence and association with gut bacteriome in patients with Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS), a functional disorder with inflammatory signs affecting 10% of the European population.

Methodology: Adult patients participated in a randomised, double-blind, cross-over, interventional trial of Faecal Microbiota Transplantation (FMT) for treating IBS. The FMT intervention was mixed microbiota from eight healthy donors; the placebo was the same mixture but autoclaved. Allocation groups varied in the order of FMT received. Specific real-time PCR detected and quantified the protists, and 16S rDNA profiling served for bacteriome analysis.

Results: Stool samples from IBS patients (n=58; median age 35) were analysed. The subject-wise prevalence was 10.3% for *Blastocystis* sp. (6/58) and 13.8% (8/58) for *D. fragilis*. The protists quantity was affected neither by active microbiota nor placebo. Positivity of the protists was marginally influenced by active microbiota (P=0.071) and associated with increased bacteriome diversity on genus level (P<0.044 across multiple indices) and with several bacterial genera (P<0.03) regardless of the intervention status.

Conclusion: The prevalence of *Blastocystis* sp. and *D. fragilis* in IBS patients is low, and their colonisation is unaffected by FMT. As expected, their presence was associated with high bacteriome diversity but was surprisingly inversely associated with some beneficial taxa.

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Talk 06 (T06)

Frequency of *Blastocystis* in vulnerable Mexican population and its association with their health status

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Abstract

Blastocystis is considered the main protist that parasitizes the human intestine and a wide range of animals. Although *Blastocystis* has been implicated as a cause of several gastrointestinal tract symptoms, its role as a pathogen remains unclear. Factors that favor the transmission of *Blastocystis* have been established, such as lack of hygiene, consumption of contaminated food and zoonotic contact. But there are also other conditions that must be considered in the transmission of *Blastocystis*, such as the vulnerability of certain groups to becoming infected by *Blastocystis* and its probable impact on their health status. The objective of this work is to determine the frequency of *Blastocystis* infection in vulnerable groups of the Mexican population, school children from a subrural community in the state of Morelos and patients diagnosed with HIV/AIDS from a public hospital in Mexico City, and to analyze their association with their health status, 294 schoolchildren between 4-15 years old and 163 patients with HIV/AIDS were studied, in whom the presence of *Blastocystis* was determined by PCR (*SSU-rDNA*-barcoding). To establish the health status of the participants, the following variables were considered: body mass index (BMI) and hemoglobin level of the schoolchildren and the stage of the disease according to the classification of Castro et al. for patients diagnosed with HIV/AIDS. Concluding, for our studied groups, being infected by *Blastocystis* had no impact on their health status, versus having a pathogenic character; it may be acting as a health indicator.

Grants: IN217821, IV200420 and IN219624 from PAPIIT- DGAPA-UNAM.

Talk 07 (T07)

Relationship between *Blastocystis* infection and clinical outcomes: A comprehensive systematic review

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* is a common eukaryotic inhabitant of the human gastrointestinal tract, with variable prevalence rates globally. Despite the recent studies that suggest its commensal role, *Blastocystis* has been related to gastrointestinal symptoms, raising questions about its pathogenic potential. However, there is ongoing debate regarding the clinical significance of *Blastocystis*. Given the conflicting evidence and lack of consensus on its pathogenicity, there is a critical need for a systematic review to evaluate existing evidence and clarify its relationship with human health outcomes. This protocol aims to lay the foundations of a systematic review that comprehensively assesses the available literature, addressing knowledge gaps and providing insights for clinical practice and public health interventions.

Methods (Protocol): This systematic review will follow PRISMA guidelines. Research question: "What is the relationship between *Blastocystis* infection and clinical outcomes in humans, and what evidence exists regarding its pathogenicity?" Include original research in humans, regardless of symptoms, confirming *Blastocystis* infection. Exclusion criteria: reviews, animal studies, non-original data, and non-English articles. Conduct a comprehensive search of PubMed, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library using relevant terms. Selection: Two reviewers screen titles/abstracts, followed by a full-text review of potentially eligible studies. Any discrepancies will be resolved through discussion and consensus. Data Extraction: Standardized form for study characteristics, participant demographics, diagnostic methods, symptoms, and outcomes. Quality Assessment: Newcastle-OTawa Scale for observational studies, Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for trials. Synthesis: Narrative synthesis; meta-analysis if possible. Reporting: Adhere to PRISMA. Consultation: Seek stakeholder feedback.

Talk 08 (T08)

Molecular, structural and functional characterization of the superoxide dismutases of the enteric protozoa *Blastocystis* sp.

Constance Denoyelle¹, Nausicaa Gantois¹, Ruben Garcia Dominguez¹, René Wintjens², Jeremy Desramaut¹, Gabriel Billon³, Gabriela Certad¹, Damien Devos¹, Magali Chabé¹, Eric Viscoglisi¹

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Abstract

As part of the interaction between *Blastocystis* and its intestinal environment, the parasite defense against oxidative stress represents a key step in its survival and colonization. The study of this machinery was initiated by the characterization of the enzymes representing the first defense barrier of the parasite, the superoxide dismutases (SODs). Three SOD genes have been identified in the available *Blastocystis* genomes. SOD1 and SOD2 are dimeric iron-containing SODs (FeSODs) protecting the cytosol and mitochondria, respectively, while SOD3 would be a cytosolic dimeric copper/zinc-containing SOD (Cu/ZnSOD). However, certain residues conserved for all Cu/ZnSODs involved in the binding of cofactor metals are absent for this SOD3. A phylogenetic analysis demonstrated that these SODs would represent excellent molecular markers for studying the evolution of subtypes (STs) within the *Blastocystis* genus. Three-dimensional models of these SODs were built using artificial intelligence AlphaFold2. SOD1 and SOD2 share all characteristics of dimeric FeSODs and would be active whereas the mutations observed for SOD3 would not allow copper fixation as evidenced by ICP-MS. *In vitro* production of the 3 SODs of *Blastocystis* ST4 in a bacterial expression system, enzymatic activity tests were carried out with the affinity chromatography-purified SODs, showing strong activity of SOD1 and SOD2 and no activity for SOD3. In parallel, overexpression of the *SOD1* and *SOD2* genes was observed in parasite cultures under oxidative stress. Our data suggest that SOD1 and SOD2 play a key role in protecting *Blastocystis* against oxidative stress while the potential role of SOD3 remains unknown.

Talk 09 (T09)

A preliminary insight in the gut microbiome profile in *Blastocystis*-carrier patients with diarrhoea in Italy

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Gut microbiome (GM) is a diverse and complex ecosystem involved in beneficial physiological functions as well as disease pathogenesis. *Blastocystis* sp. is a common protozoan parasite and is increasingly recognized as an important GM component. Despite recent studies suggesting *Blastocystis* sp. decreases the beneficial bacteria abundance, the understanding of their relationship with other GM communities is still so far. This work aims trying to better understand the role of *Blastocystis* sp. and the interactions with the GM community in a cohort of patients with diarrheal diseases in Italy.

Methods: Over a period 2022-2024, consecutive, non-replicated diarrhoeic faecal samples were subjected to Allplex™ GI Parasite Platform. Furthermore, 16S rRNA gene amplification and sequencing by Oxford Nanopore Technologies platform (EPI2ME software) was performed on a sub-sample of ten *Blastocystis*-carrier patients, homogenous by age and gender, to profile and compare their GM.

Results: Out of 1181 faecal samples, 75 (6.3%) were found positive to *Blastocystis* sp., (73.2% single infection and 26.8% enteric protozoa co-infection). A higher abundant bacterial diversity was recorded for *Streptococcus*, *Bacteroides* and *Oscillibacter* (at genus level) and *Escherichia fergusonii*, *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and *Succinivibrio dextrinosolvens* (at species level) were found within our sub-samples and with a significant association with eosinophilia level ($p=0.02359$).

Conclusions: Our results are not in accordance with previous evidence according to which, *Blastocystis* sp. colonisation would be linked with an eubiotic gut characterized by potentially beneficial species such as *Prevotella* and *Ruminococcus*. Further investigations with larger samples size are needed to better clarify the eubiotic or dysbiotic state of *Blastocystis* sp.

Talk 10 (T10)

No association between *Blastocystis* carriage and colorectal cancer in a cohort of Colombian patients

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* is a major colonizer of the human gastrointestinal tract whose role as an agent of gastroenteritis remains controversial. However, some studies have suggested its contribution to the severity of multiple conditions, such as AIDs, irritable bowel syndrome, and cancer, in particular colorectal cancer (CRC). CRC is the third most common cancer and the second leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide. This study investigates whether *Blastocystis* and other intestinal microorganisms could increase the likelihood of developing CRC.

Methods: Stool samples were collected from patients undergoing CRC screening with a normal colonoscopy (non-CRC group) and patients with cancer (CRC group) at five hospitals in Medellín, Colombia. Informed consents and epidemiologic surveys were collected from all the participants. The presence of intestinal parasitic and bacterial agents was investigated by conventional (microscopy, Jones' medium culture for *Blastocystis*) and molecular (PCR and next-generation sequencing) techniques.

Results: A total of 308 (154 non-CRC, 154 CRC) patients paired for sex and age were included in the study. *Blastocystis* was the most prevalent agent found (111, 36.0%), followed by enteroaggregative *Escherichia coli* (48, 15.6%), diffusely adherent *E. coli* (39, 12.7%), and *Giardia duodenalis* (23, 7.5%). *Blastocystis* was detected at similar proportions in both non-CRC and CRC groups. However, CRC patients were more likely to harbour *Streptococcus gallolyticus* subsp. *pasteurianus* (9.7%, 15/154 vs. 2.6%, 4/154, $p = 0.009$) and *Morganella morganii* (6.5%, 10/154 vs. 1.3%, 2/154, $p = 0.018$) than non-CRC patients.

Conclusion: According to our results, *Blastocystis* infection does not predispose to the development of CRC.

Talk 11 (T11)

From land to sea: The long journey of *Blastocystis* sp.

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Abstract

Blastocystis sp. is frequently identified in humans and several animal hosts and exhibits a large genetic diversity. In the perspective of the One Health approach, data on the distribution of *Blastocystis* sp. and its circulating subtypes from the terrestrial environment are available, while those from the marine environment remain still unknown. In order to better understand the epidemiology of this microorganism across different host species and its potential zoonotic transmission, a large-scale survey was conducted from land to sea by screening faecal samples from humans and four species of free-ranging marine mammals (sperm, fin, long-finned pilot and Cuvier's beaked whales). The samples were collected from Northern to Southern Italy and subjected to real-time Allplex™ GI Parasites Platform and SSU-rDNA gene amplification and sequencing over the period 2022-2024. Out of 1181 human faecal samples, 75 (6.3%) were found positive to *Blastocystis* sp., with ST1 (allele 4), ST2 (alleles 9, 13), ST3 (alleles 34, 36) and ST4 (allele 92) detected, with varying distribution across human samples. Out of 43 marine-mammal faecal samples, 10 (23.2%) were found positive to *Blastocystis* sp. with ST3 the most detected subtype among the different species of marine mammals. Furthermore, all of the ST3 sequences were phylogenetically placed within a unique clade. The present survey provides new insights regarding *Blastocystis* prevalence and its circulating subtypes from the marine environment with a potential zoonotic transmission to human. In addition, these results present the first new hosts record and extend the known host range of this zoonotic protozoan parasite.

Talk 12 (T12)

From parasite to protector? *Blastocystis* and gut health: Insights from the DanFunD study

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Abstract

Blastocystis is one of the world's most successful human parasites and yet the presence of *Blastocystis* may provide a protective effect against the development of intestinal disease, including inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). This project investigates the relationship between *Blastocystis*, gut health, and eubiosis through the analysis of 2,460 participant fecal samples from the Danish epidemiological study of Functional Disorders (DanFunD). DanFunD samples are accompanied by comprehensive epidemiological data, including biochemical analysis of blood and urine, health examination data, diet, and other environmental factors. Fecal samples will be analyzed via 16S/18S small subunit rRNA amplicon sequencing of the V3, V4, and V5 hyper-variable regions, allowing for subtype-level resolution of *Blastocystis* species. Raw sequencing data will be processed using the BION metagenomic pipeline and mapped to the RDP and SILVA reference databases for taxonomic assignment. Results will be paired with the DanFunD's robust epidemiological data creating a comprehensive analysis of the impact of *Blastocystis* on bacterial microbiota, other gut eukaryotes, alpha and beta diversity, and gut health. While this project is ongoing, preliminary results are available for analysis. Expected results include detailed descriptions of: 1) *Blastocystis* prevalence in the Danish population; and 2) the characteristics of *Blastocystis* carriers, including their microbiome profile, clinical parameters, and overall health. Given the statistical power afforded by the sample size and the extensive epidemiological data, this project will help to reshape our understanding of the role *Blastocystis* plays within the human gut and opportunities for treating e.g., IBD.

Talk 13 (T13)

Genetic diversity of *Blastocystis* and associated microbiome among patients with immune-mediated inflammatory diseases, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Introduction: There is a worldwide unexplained increase in both gut and systemic immune-mediated inflammatory diseases (IMID). This study's goal is to detect the genetic diversity of *Blastocystis* in patients with IMID. Also, to assess the association between *Blastocystis* colonization and patient data, including gut microbiome.

Methodology: Fecal specimens and related data were collected from >2,500 patients attending a university hospital in the Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia. Stool specimens were microscopically examined for pathogens and cultured for *Blastocystis*. *Blastocystis* and protozoal DNAs were amplified using PCR assays, followed by genotyping. Obtained DNA products are in the process of being amplicon sequenced for gut bacteria, targeting the 16S rRNA gene, and gut eukaryotes (fungi), targeting the ITS sequence.

Results: *Blastocystis* species were the most prevailing pathogen of studied populations, and much more prevalent in healthy individuals than patients with IMIDs. Other parasitic infections were sporadic among the study population. Both IMIDs and *Blastocystis* distribution showed patterns among different age groups and sex. Data from microbiome analysis and its relation to the occurrence of *Blastocystis* will be presented.

Discussion: To our knowledge, this is the first extensive study in Saudi Arabia identifying *Blastocystis* species in IMIDs. There is a high prevalence of IMIDs and *Blastocystis* infection rate among study populations. *Blastocystis* was more predominant in healthy individuals than in patients with GIT disorders. Pathogenicity may be related to *Blastocystis* subtypes. Further genetic studies to assess *Blastocystis* distribution and role in health and disease will provide a better understanding of *Blastocystis* transmission dynamics.

Talk 14 (T14)

Application of the anti-amoebic methodology in drug discovery against *Blastocystis*

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Abstract

One of our main research lines is the drug discovery against various protozoal organisms including pathogenic Free Living Amoebae (FLA) genus. FLA are ubiquitous protozoa parasite widely distributed in the environment, including some that can cause opportunistic infections in humans and other animals. Among the known FLA genus, *Acanthamoeba* genus was the most isolated amoeba from environmental habitats and clinical cases.

As a member of a research group with a long track record in the study of free-living amoebae including drug discovery. Our main objective is to apply our knowledge in anti-amoebic field towards *Blastocystis* spp. Although, the life cycle of this unicellular parasite is more complex and still not well defined, the existence of an amoeboid form would allow us to study the *in vitro* activity using the same methodology as FLA. Still, we need to understand much better the life cycle of this protozoa parasite to be able to optimize the *in vitro* activity.

Talk 15 (T15)

Investigating parasitic diseases in Iraq under One Health perspective

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Abstract

This study investigates the prevalence of *Cryptosporidium*, *Blastocystis*, *Giardia*, and *Entamoeba histolytica* in humans, animals, and the environment in a rural area in Iraq.

In total, 140 samples were collected from a village near the Iraqi-Irani border of which 50 were from humans, 50 from their animals (35 sheep and 15 goats), 20 from soil, and another 20 from water. Microscopic examination of human stool revealed infection rates of 12% in the case of *Cryptosporidium*, 16% for *Blastocystis*, and 10% for *Giardia*. In animals, the rates were *Cryptosporidium* 26%, *Blastocystis* 78%, and *Giardia* 8%. Soil samples showed *Cryptosporidium* 5%, *Blastocystis* 45%, while 15% of water samples were positive for *Cryptosporidium* and 5% for *Blastocystis*. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was used on all samples to amplify the *18S rRNA* gene and 60-kDa glycoprotein gene (*gp60*) of *Cryptosporidium*, the *18S rRNA* gene of *Blastocystis* and the beta-giardin (*bg*) and triosephosphate isomerase (*tpi*) of *Giardia*. Using qPCR of the *bg* gene, 30% of human samples were positive for *Giardia*, 14% of animals, and 2% of soil. *Entamoeba histolytica* was not detected in any of the samples. Sanger sequencing has so far revealed that 2% of sheep were infected with *Cryptosporidium ubiquitum*, while *Cryptosporidium parvum* was found in 16% of humans and 2% of animals all of which were sheep. *Blastocystis* subtype (ST)1 was found in humans, whereas ST4 and ST10 were detected in sheep. For *Giardia intestinalis*, only one type was found in sheep. The presence of *C. parvum* in humans and animals living in the same community suggests zoonosis.

Talk 16 (T16)

Meta-analysis of *Blastocystis* subtype distribution and prevalence across hosts and geographic regions: Advancing knowledge through interdisciplinary collaboration and data visualisation

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Abstract

Blastocystis is a controversial parasite found in the intestinal tract in both human and non-human hosts. The diversity of *Blastocystis* has allowed for scientists to classify numerous subtypes (STs) over the past few years. Interdisciplinary studies have significantly advanced our understanding of the parasite, elucidating some of its behavioural patterns and genetic characteristics. However, despite the studies constantly referencing each other, over the last decade there has not been a single study focusing on all the STs identified by data already submitted, providing a comprehensive understanding of their prevalence and distribution across countries and hosts. This research is a meta-analysis of 18S rRNA sequences submitted to GenBank, which will provide a study where scientists interested in *Blastocystis* can access previous data categorised based on the STs identified, the country/continent the data was collected from, the host the parasite as found in and access numbers in case further details are needed from the original database (such as full sequences). The second aim is to provide visual representations of trends and patterns detected using data analysis software such as RStudio and Python, allowing the easy recognition of subtype prevalence patterns in each country already studied. As of yet, the analysis of the data and graphs generated have allowed the recognition of patterns that suggest host specificity in ST prevalence. It is hoped that the introduction of statistical analysis (Bayesian statistics) will not only further explain the relationship between ST prevalence, host and country, but also allow the prediction of future infection patterns.

Talk 17 (T17)

Molecular characterization of *Blastocystis* from human, animal and environmental samples from Turkiye

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Abstract

Blastocystis is a protist of controversial pathogenicity commonly found in the gastrointestinal tract of a variety of vertebrate hosts, including humans and other mammals, as well as birds, reptiles, fish and insects. Despite intense research efforts, our understanding of its biology and transmission dynamics remains incomplete. Previous studies in Colombia and Thailand indicated circulation of the organism between vertebrate hosts and the environment. In this study, we undertake a One Health approach to investigate the transmission dynamics of *Blastocystis* between human-animal and environmental ecosystems in a rural area in Turkiye. The study area comprised of a settlement near the Seyhan Dam Lake of Kırıklı village, Adana Province. A total of 429 stool samples were collected, of which 124 were from humans, 151 from sheep, 89 from cattle and 65 from goats. Forty dam water samples were also collected. All samples were screened for *Blastocystis* using real-time PCR (RT-PCR). The prevalence of *Blastocystis* was found to be 89,5% (111/124) in humans and 100% in cattle (89/89), sheep (151/151), goats (64/64) and also dam water materials (40/40). Subtype analysis is ongoing and will be discussed. This research highlights the significance of a One Health viewpoint in uncovering the transmission dynamics of *Blastocystis*.

Financial support: This study was supported by TUBITAK 1002 Quick Support Program (Project no: 123S965).

Talk 28 (T18)

***Blastocystis* in cattle: a providential game changer to limit global warming**

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Abstract

Blastocystis, the most prevalent protozoan in human stools, is increasingly recognized as a commensal member of our gut microbiome, being associated with hallmarks of a healthy gut, like an increased gut bacterial diversity in asymptomatic individuals. In this study, we focused on the impact of *Blastocystis* in dairy cattle. Thanks to a collaboration with a company specializing in livestock genomic selection, we had access to a large cohort of 1,581 fecal samples from non-pregnant, non-diarrheic Prim'Holstein dairy cows bred in 20 commercial herds from the North of France. The cows were sampled between 2017 and 2018 but their zootechnical performances were surveyed until the end of their dairy production career. Fecal samples were tested for the presence of *Blastocystis* and their associated fecal bacterial microbiota. We found a prevalence of *Blastocystis* of 54.8 % in the dairy cows. As in humans, we demonstrated that bacterial alpha-diversity was higher in the fecal microbiota of *Blastocystis* colonized cows than in cows without it. Also, by studying heifers specifically, we found that the presence of *Blastocystis* at the heifer stage was associated with a 22% higher productive longevity without compromising the daily milk yield and a 17.5 % lower carbon contribution per kg of milk produced, than in *Blastocystis*-free dairy cows. Thus, we were able to conclude that *Blastocystis* was an early indicator for productive longevity in dairy cows and a game changer to limit cattle CH₄ emissions. This result became an invention, which we protected with a European patent, currently under PCT.

Talk 19 (T19)

Worldwide presence of *Blastocystis* in the human gut microbiome is linked to healthier diets and more favorable cardiometabolic outcomes.

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Abstract

The human gut microbiome is a diverse community of microorganisms that inhabit the human gastrointestinal tract and influence host physiology. Shotgun metagenomic sequencing enables high-resolution profiling of all the members of this community. While the bacterial fraction has been extensively investigated in relation to human health, organisms from other domains are currently underexplored. *Blastocystis* is a micro-eukaryote that has shown contrasting associations with both gastrointestinal symptoms and favorable cardiometabolic profiles. To investigate *Blastocystis*' role in host health, we performed a computational analysis of over 60,000 metagenomic samples. We observed a widespread presence of *Blastocystis* among healthy individuals, with prevalence variability linked to host age, lifestyle, and geographical provenance. We found that individuals consuming healthier diets rich in plant-based and unprocessed foods were more likely to be *Blastocystis*-positive. Furthermore, *Blastocystis* presence was associated with more favorable short-term cardiometabolic markers, such as lower GlycA and higher HDL levels. Meta-analyses revealed a robust association between *Blastocystis* carriage and lower BMI values, as well as reduced risk for disorders linked to altered gut ecology. Moreover, in a diet intervention study of 1,124 individuals, we observed that improvements in dietary quality were linked to weight reductions and increases in *Blastocystis* prevalence and abundance. Finally, machine learning models accurately predicted *Blastocystis* presence and revealed a common signature of previously undescribed microbiome species across datasets. Overall, our results suggest a potentially beneficial role for gut *Blastocystis*. Further genomic and functional analyses are needed to characterize different *Blastocystis* subtypes and to elucidate acquisition and transmission routes.

Talk 20 (T20)

***Blastocystis* and the gut microbiome: metagenomic and metatranscriptomic study of *Blastocystis*-colonized rat gut**

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Abstract

Blastocystis hominis, an anaerobic microbial eukaryote of the lineage Stramenopila, lives as an intestinal endobiont in various animals, including humans. While traditionally considered a pathogen associated with gastrointestinal symptoms such as nausea, diarrhea, and vomiting, recent evidence challenges this view due to its high prevalence among healthy, asymptomatic individuals. Despite the growing number of studies, the question of *Blastocystis*' influence on the human gut microbiome and human health remains unresolved. Building upon our previous study that demonstrated the protective effect of *Blastocystis* against induced colitis in rats, we employed a similar experimental laboratory model to investigate its relationship with the prokaryotic gut microflora. Utilizing metagenomic and metatranscriptomic data from rat ceca infected and uninfected with *Blastocystis*, we aim to elucidate the impact of *Blastocystis* presence on the composition and transcriptional profile of the gut microbiome.

Talk 21 (T21)

Metagenomics, metabolomics and transcriptomics as a tool to better understand the role of *Blastocystis* in the gastrointestinal environment

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Abstract

The fundamental role of *Blastocystis* in the gastrointestinal environment remains elusive: it is unclear whether this microbial eukaryote engineers the composition of the surrounding ecosystem, or whether it is merely responsive to changes in this environment. Metagenomics, metabolomics and transcriptomics are three key 'omics' techniques we will use to uncover the *in vitro* biology of *Blastocystis*. Xenic cultures of *Blastocystis* ST1-ST9 were maintained over six days to investigate any changes to the microbiome, metabolome and transcriptome. DNA extractions were performed and sent for 16S-amplicon metagenomic sequencing to decipher the prokaryotic composition present in *in vitro* cultures. Metabolite extractions were carried out, and relative metabolite abundances were detected using 1D proton NMR, to help map the metabolic processes taking place between *Blastocystis* and the surrounding microorganisms in static culture. Preliminary microbiome analysis shows that the prokaryotic composition differed significantly from the rest of the subtypes for ST3 at feature-level and ST6 at species level. Similarly, differences were identified in the metabolome data. This study's integration of metagenomics, metabolomics, and transcriptomics provides a multi-dimensional view of *Blastocystis*' interactions within the microbial ecosystem, illustrating subtype-specific relationships and their potential impacts on microbial community structure and function. The distinct microbial and metabolic signatures associated with different *Blastocystis* subtypes suggest that this protist may play a role in shaping the gastrointestinal environment, rather than merely reacting to it. These insights pave the way for future research to explore the causal mechanisms behind these interactions and their implications for host health and disease.

Talk 22 (T22)

Artificial intelligence and diagnosis of *Blastocystis* in the hospital setting: Road back to microscopy

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Abstract

Diagnosis of *Blastocystis* species in clinical fecal specimens continues to be challenging. Clinical implications, challenges, and limitations of old and new fecal diagnostic methods will be discussed based on our two decades of clinical experience both in hospital settings and in clinical research. We will present our newly developed molecular nano-based technique that can be used as a point-of-care test.

Currently, many diagnostic approaches are used for the diagnosis of *Blastocystis* species in fecal clinical samples, including conventional microscopy and immunodiagnosics as well as molecular diagnostics, all of which contain challenges and limitations.

In the last few years, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based automated digital imaging, syndromic panels, and next-generation genome sequencing techniques coupled with bioinformatics data analysis have undergone huge advances. They have revolutionized diagnosis, are one of the most promising applications, and will continue to be the next frontier in diagnostic parasitology. These new techniques with automation open new horizons in developing affordable, versatile, and user-friendly interface applications. This makes sophisticated steps of diagnostics easy to perform without expertise and decreases the need for pre-analytical sample preparation. This facilitates the implementation of these novel diagnostic techniques in different healthcare facilities, including limited resource settings, with a positive impact on patient care. Notwithstanding, the challenges and limitations of these techniques need to be addressed.

Despite the benefits of these new technologies, expert parasitologists will always be needed throughout incorporating and implementing these new techniques.

Talk 23 (T23)

An overview of *Blastocystis* epidemiology from One Health perspective

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Abstract

Blastocystis, a common intestinal protist found in humans and animals, presents significant challenges in epidemiology due to its diverse host range and unclear pathogenicity. From a “One Health” perspective, which integrates human, animal, and environmental health, understanding *Blastocystis* is crucial for understanding transmission dynamics and host-protist interactions, thereby clarifying the clinical and public health significance.

Blastocystis is globally distributed, with prevalence rates varying by region, often higher in developing areas. Currently, at least 42 genetic subtypes (STs) exist and ST1 to ST4 are predominantly found in humans, while others infect a range of animals and rarely humans.

To improve of the knowledge for *Blastocystis* epidemiology is needed a One Health approach, involving surveillance across human, animal, and environmental components. New strategies for focusing on the molecular epidemiology of *Blastocystis* are essential, especially for detecting *Blastocystis* subtypes and intrasubtype variations, providing an understanding of the characteristics of *Blastocystis*.

Developing and disseminating strategies to determine the molecular epidemiology of *Blastocystis* within a One Health perspective will enable the identification of the distribution of subtypes and intrasubtype variations across different geographic regions, thereby clarifying the transmission dynamics and zoonotic potential, monitoring the reservoirs of this protist.

In providing the necessary data for *Blastocystis* epidemiology, it is very important for researchers to use standardized methods for an effective analysis of the results, preventing variability due to methodology.

Poster 01 (P01)

***Blastocystis* carriage and molecular diversity in Zambian asymptomatic schoolchildren**

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Abstract

Little information is currently available on the presence and molecular diversity of *Blastocystis* sp. in human populations from sub-Saharan African countries. In Zambia, *Blastocystis* carriage and molecular diversity has been only investigated in individuals with clinical manifestations. In this cross-sectional survey, individual stool samples from 256 apparently healthy schoolchildren (median age: 9.0 years; range: 5-18; male/female ratio: 1.1) attending two public schools in the localities of Chongwe ($n = 111$) and Kafue ($n = 145$) were investigated during April-August 2023. Detection of *Blastocystis* was conducted by PCR using pan-*Blastocystis*, barcode primers BhRDr/RD5, and confirmation and subtype (ST) identification by Sanger sequence analyses.

Overall, 45.3% (116/256; 95% CI: 39.3–51.6) of the participating children were *Blastocystis*-positive. Sequence analyses revealed the presence of only three different STs including ST1 (33.6%, 39/116), ST2 (43.1%, 50/116) and ST3 (18.1%, 21/116). Five samples (4.3%, 5/116) corresponded to mixed infections by unknown STs (identified as overlapping chromatograms). A single sample (0.9%, 1/116) was untypable due to low sequence quality. Additionally, 51 samples (19.9%, 51/256) yielded unreadable chromatograms and were conservatively considered negative. Children living in Kafue were more likely to carry *Blastocystis* [$\chi^2 (1, n = 256) = 11.61, p = 0.00066$]. Gender, age group, and contact with domestic animals were not significantly associated with an increased likelihood of harbouring *Blastocystis*.

Blastocystis carriage was a common finding in the surveyed Zambian, apparently healthy, schoolchildren population. Absence of animal-adapted subtypes (e.g., ST5-ST8) seems to indicate that *Blastocystis* transmission is primarily anthroponotic in this epidemiological scenario.

Poster 02 (P02)

***Blastocystis hominis* diagnosis in a low prevalence setting: evaluation of the impact of formalin-free fixative and the number of specimens/episode using a commercial single-vial in a referral laboratory**

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Abstract

Background: Commercial single-vials including fixative have simplified the workflow in the laboratory stool concentration to perform microscopic examination. Recently, new fixatives formalin-free have been appeared. In this study we evaluate the performance of a formalin-free fixative and the number of specimens per episode for *Blastocystis hominis* (BH) diagnosis using commercial single-vials.

Methods: A retrospective longitudinal study was performed at the Microbiology Department of Vall d'Hebron University Hospital (Barcelona) from January 2018 to December 2019. From January- 2018 to March-2019 stool samples were collected in formalin-based fixative vials (Midi Parasep® Solvent free) and three specimen/episode were preferred. From April-2019 to December-2019 an alcohol-based formalin free fixative (Midi Parasep® Alcorfix™) was used and one specimen/episode was preferred. Lugol staining was performed for microscopic examination.

Results: 56068 stool specimens concerning 27912 episodes for protozoa investigation were included. BH was detected in 18.8% of episodes (5260/27912).

Irrespective of the number of specimens per episode: comparing the formalin-based periods (January-March), no significant differences on BH detection were observed (21.8% versus 23.7%, $p=0.063$) whereas comparing formalin-based versus formalin-free fixative periods (May-December), a significant decrease was observed (22.4% versus 13.0%, $p=0.000$).

Significant higher BH detection rates were observed in 3-specimen/episode versus 1-specimen/episode (24.3% versus 18.9% with formalin-based; 15.6% versus 11.9% with Alcorfix™). Cumulative percentage of BH detection in formalin-based 3-specimen episodes based on adding 1st, 2nd and 3rd specimens were 22.8%, 23.9%, 24.4% ($p=0.007$).

Conclusions: BH detection was impaired by using Alcorfix™ fixative and by the reduction of the number of specimens per episode.

Poster 03 (P03)

***Blastocystis hominis* frequency: Effects on clinical manifestations and infection outcomes in humans**

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Abstract

Background: Lack of consistency in *Blastocystis hominis* protocols in *developing* countries, although clinical manifestations of *Blastocystis* spp. are frequently ambiguous, has resulted in missing and misinterpreted data. Our aim is to assess *B. hominis* prevalence and clinical symptoms in suspected patients.

Methods: This is a year-long descriptive study at Cambridge Clinical Laboratories. Stool samples from 842 gastrointestinal suspected patients were microscopically examined using zinc sulphate flotation and iodine-stained preparations.

Results: Out of 842 patients suspected of gastrointestinal parasite, the average resulted 32.5±11.2 with min 3 years and max 72 years old. The prevalence rate for gastrointestinal parasites resulted 37.76% (318/842), where *Giardia lamblia* and *Blastocystis hominis* were the most prevalent parasites (19.6% and 6.17% respectively). Related the gender positivity, male 62.58% (199/318) and female 37.42% (119/318) without significant ($\chi^2=0.83$; $p=0.20$).

Out of 52 *B. hominis* positive patients, 55.77% (29/52) were males, 44.23% (23/52) were female without significant association ($\chi^2=0.71$; $p=0.26$). Patients in age 25-35 years resulted with high prevalence compared to other age groups (41.4%) ($\chi^2=89.2$; $p=0.01$). A significant association was found between the positivity for *B. hominis* and clinical manifestation vis asymptomatic patients for p value < 0.05. Abdominal pain (31.9%) was the most frequent clinical manifestation, followed by acute diarrhea (23.5%), nausea (11.2%), anorexia (8.4%) and irritable bowel syndrome (5.7%).

Conclusion: Even though *B. hominis* is an underappreciated parasite in Albania, the clinical symptoms and infection outcomes in suspected patients are extremely concerning. To reduce the significant risk of transmission, up-to-date knowledge of laboratory must be applied.

Poster 04 (P04)

***Blastocystis* infection in Polish soldiers stationed in the Republic of Kosovo and Lebanon**

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Abstract

Blastocystis is the most common protozoan found in the intestines of humans and animals. Since soldiers participating in military operations are particularly vulnerable to infection, this study was undertaken to identify and subtype *Blastocystis* sp. in Polish troops participating in peacekeeping missions in the Republic of Kosovo and Lebanon.

Faecal samples were collected from 108 and 192 soldiers stationed respectively in Lebanon and Kosovo in a period of November 2020 – February 2021. Each soldier was tested twice on arrival and after four months of stay. Material was fixed in 70 % ethanol. After DNA extraction, the barcoding region of the small subunit ribosomal RNA (*SSU-rRNA*) gene was amplified and sequenced using Sanger method.

The DNA of *Blastocystis* was detected in six (3.13%) and three (1.10%) samples in the first batch and in thirty (15.16%) and nine (8.33%) samples in the second batch collected in Kosovo and Lebanon, respectively. Sequencing revealed infections with ST 2, 3, 4, and 7 in Kosovo and ST2 and 3 in Lebanon, with predominance of ST3. The results indicate that the visit to a new environment and prolonged stay in the area of military operations resulted in a significant increase in *Blastocystis* infections in soldiers. ST diversity was greater among soldiers stationed in Kosovo, which may be due to a different organization of bases, including contact with the civilian population and local food.

Financial support: project of the Military Institute of Medicine in Warsaw (No 573) and Polish Ministry of Science and Higher Education (MUG ST 02-0104/772).

Poster 05 (P05)

***Blastocystis* is very rare in faeces of children with Crohn's disease: quantity, subtyping and association with the faecal bacteriome**

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Abstract

Background: As an indicator of gut health, *Blastocystis* is being studied among multiple diagnoses in adults; however, studies in children are generally lacking. Therefore, we aimed to assess its occurrence and subtypes in a longitudinal set of faecal samples from children with Crohn's disease (CD) and compare them to similar collections from children having other chronic immunopathological diseases without gut pathology (type 1 diabetes [T1D], and juvenile idiopathic arthritis [JIA]), and healthy controls.

Methods: Specific real-time PCR detected and quantified *Blastocystis*, whereas massively parallel amplicon sequencing showed its subtype. The relationship between *Blastocystis* and the bacterial community was assessed by 16S rDNA profiling.

Results: In total, 626 samples were collected from 156 subjects. Subject-wise positivity of *Blastocystis* in CD (3/40, 7.5%) was significantly lower than in either T1D (21/57, 37%), JIA (2/10, 20%), or in healthy controls (14/49, 29%). There was no notable difference in the subtype repertoires among diagnoses. *Blastocystis*-positive samples had higher alpha diversity and slightly yet significantly ($p < 0.001$) different overall community composition across all diagnoses, which was reflected by the differential abundance of several taxa.

Conclusions: *Blastocystis* is very rare among paediatric patients with CD, in contrast to two other chronic immunopathologic childhood diagnoses. Further longitudinal observation will show whether *Blastocystis* might return in patients with well-controlled CD upon ameliorating their bacteriome composition.

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Poster 06 (P06)

***Blastocystis* occurrence and subtype diversity in wild ungulates in Spain**

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Abstract

Blastocystis is a microeukaryote capable of colonising the gastrointestinal tract of humans and animals worldwide. Little information is currently available on the occurrence and molecular diversity of *Blastocystis* in wildlife and the role of free-living host species as sources of environmental contamination and, consequently, potential human infections. The increase of wild ungulate populations across Europe has raised concerns about their role in the spread of infectious diseases, particularly those with zoonotic significance. Faecal samples ($n = 1,059$) from wild ungulate species were collected across Spain during the period 1999–2021). Using conventional PCR and next-generation amplicon sequencing, *Blastocystis* was found in 9.3% (99/1,059; 95% CI: 7.7–11.3) of the samples analysed, including 10.0% (36/360; 95% CI: 7.31–13.5) of wild boars and 9.0% (63/699; 95% CI: 7.1–11.4%) of wild ruminants, respectively. Sixteen *Blastocystis* STs (ST2, ST5, ST10a/b, ST13, ST14, ST15, ST21, ST23, ST24a/b/c, ST25, ST26, ST30, ST31, ST42b, ST43, and ST44) were identified among the surveyed wild ungulate populations, with a higher variability of STs found in wild ruminants than in wild boars. ST5 was found in all *Blastocystis*-positive wild boars, supporting the host preference of this subtype. Mixed infections were found in 17.2% (17/99) of all *Blastocystis*-positive samples. These results improve considerably our current understanding of the *Blastocystis* epidemiology and ST diversity in wild ungulates from Spain, providing molecular-based evidence of i) cross-species transmission and ii) *Blastocystis* ST preference for certain host species.

Poster 07 (P07)

***Blastocystis*: Its role in gastrointestinal health and post-cholecystectomy colonisation**

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Abstract

Blastocystis is the most prevalent eukaryotic microbe in the human gut, colonising between one and two billion people worldwide. Its role in gastrointestinal health remains controversial; it is associated with both symptomatic enteric conditions and a healthy gut microbiome. Previous research has predominantly focused on its presence in individuals with conditions like irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). This study marks the first to investigate the changes in *Blastocystis* colonisation and overall microbiome composition in patients diagnosed with cholelithiasis (gallstones).

We collected at least 75 stool samples from participants before, immediately after, and six months following cholecystectomy. DNA extractions were carried out for 16S-amplicon metagenomic sequencing to monitor microbiome shifts post-surgery. Concurrently, we screened for *Blastocystis* presence, subtyping the positive cases. Metabolomic profiles were assessed using 1D-proton NMR.

Preliminary findings indicate an intriguing pattern: several patients that were *Blastocystis* negative prior to surgery showed colonisation postoperatively. We hypothesise that once we have fully analysed the data, including 16S-amplicon sequencing and metabolomics, a correlation will emerge linking *Blastocystis* colonisation with the restoration of a eubiotic gut microbiome. These results may support the notion that *Blastocystis* is a marker of gastrointestinal health, rather than a contributor to disease.

Poster 08 (P08)

Clinical scoring of symptoms of chemically induced colitis in experimental rats during colonization of the gut protist *Blastocystis*

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Abstract

Blastocystis, a common intestinal protist in humans and animals, has unclear impacts on health and the microbiome. While sometimes linked to gastrointestinal issues, it often occurs in healthy individuals. This study investigates the effects of *Blastocystis* ST3 colonization on the immune system and gut bacteriome, both alone and with DNBS-induced colitis. Female Wistar rats were inoculated with *Blastocystis* ST3 and colitis was induced at short-term (three weeks) and long-term (three months) intervals. We conducted comprehensive clinical scoring of the health status of rats, assessing weight loss, stool consistency, hematochezia, and post-dissection colon inflammation.

Results showed that short-term colonization did not affect intestinal inflammation, while long-term exposure significantly improved recovery from colitis. This was evidenced by reduced inflammatory markers (TNF α , IL-1 β) and enhanced clinical scores, indicating better overall health and reduced symptoms two days post-induction. Despite initial health declines after colitis induction, long-term colonized rats demonstrated rapid and marked recovery, with significant weight gain, reduced haematochezia, less intestinal inflammation, and increased gut length by the next day.

These findings suggest that long-term *Blastocystis* ST3 colonization may offer protective effects against intestinal inflammation, promoting faster recovery and better health outcomes. These results could potentially apply to humans, who also experience long-term colonization with *Blastocystis*. For further details on the gut bacterial microbiome, see Billy et al. (2021).

Acknowledgment: This project was financially supported by a grant from the Czech Science Foundation (no. 22-04837S) and by the grant from the Research Council of Norway (no. 324516).

Poster 09 (P09)

Comparative genotyping of *Blastocystis* infecting cattle and human in the south of Tunisia

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* sp. is currently the most common eukaryotic parasite found in humans and many animals' intestinal tract. Despite its potential public health impact, epidemiological data regarding genotypes of *Blastocystis* infecting cattle and humans in the south of Tunisia.

Methods: A total of 200 human stool samples and 175 cattle stool samples were microscopically examined for *Blastocystis* infection. DNA was extracted from thirty-eight microscopically positive samples (33 humans and 48 cattle). PCR was performed on positive samples targeting the *Blastocystis*-specific SSU rDNA gene. PCR products of eight humans and eleven cattle samples were sequenced and compared with available reference sequences in GenBank by BLAST queries. Genetic diversity was measured for *Blastocystis* subtypes in human and cattle, based on haplotype and nucleotide diversities.

Results: The PCR detected *Blastocystis* in ten humans and twenty-four cattle samples. *Blastocystis* subtypes 1, 2, and 6 were found in humans whereas subtypes 5 and 10 were found in cattle. Subtype (ST) 2 was the most predominant subtypes in humans whereas, in cattle specimens, the ST5 was the most dominant subtype. Based on the *Blastocystis* sequences of SSU rDNA, 78 sites were polymorphic and 74 sites were parsimony informative, resulting in the identification of 15 haplotypes, 12 haplotypes in the cattle and 9 in humans. No haplotype was shared between cattle and human parasites.

Conclusion: Human-derived *Blastocystis* subtypes were different from cattle subtypes in southern Tunisia. Nevertheless, subtype 5 in cattle can be a risk factor for human infection.

Poster 10 (P10)

Cross-species detection of select intestinal pathogenic parasites under One Health approach in Algeria

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Abstract

Blastocystis, *Giardia*, *Cryptosporidium*, and *Entamoeba histolytica* are common intestinal eukaryotes of humans and other animals. *Blastocystis* is a parasite of controversial pathogenicity, while the other three are causative agents of diarrhoea, particularly in areas with poor sanitation and hygiene.

This study took place in rural community in Djelfa Province in the center south of Algeria. In total, 208 fecal samples were collected, of which 25 were from humans, and 183 from their livestock (cattle=45, sheep=96, and goat=42). All samples were screened using qPCR. In humans, *Blastocystis* was detected in 31% of the samples, *Giardia* in 16%, while *Entamoeba histolytica* was not detected. In animals, the corresponding rates were 67%, 61%, and 38% for *Blastocystis*, *Cryptosporidium*, and *Giardia*, respectively. Subsequently, for subtyping, nested PCR was used on the positive samples to amplify fragments of the 18S rRNA and *gp60* of *Cryptosporidium*, the 18S rRNA of *Blastocystis*, the beta-giardin (*bg*) and triosephosphate isomerase (*tpi*) of *Giardia*. These findings reveal the widespread distribution of these parasites in humans and their livestock. Co-infections of *Blastocystis* and other eukaryotic parasites were also noted.

This study highlights the importance of considering human and animal hosts when studying disease transmission and control strategies between humans and animals.

Poster 11 (P11)

Detection and molecular characterization of *Blastocystis* species in school children living in Kosovo

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* is a unicellular anaerobic protozoan commonly found in the digestive tract of both humans and animals. Although it has been linked to different gastrointestinal disorders, the role of *Blastocystis* as a commensal or parasitic factor is not clearly defined. The aim of this study was to estimate occurrence of *Blastocystis* infection among children living in Kosovo.

Material and Methods: In total, 478 faecal samples fixed in 70% ethyl alcohol were collected from school children aged 6-15 in the community of Kaçanik, southern part of Kosovo in 2018. The samples were investigated using molecular methods including the amplification of barcoding region of the small subunit ribosomal RNA (*SSU-rRNA*) gene and Sanger sequencing.

Results: DNA of *Blastocystis* was detected in 126 (26.4%) samples tested. Sequencing of the PCR products revealed infections with ST 3, ST1 and ST2 in 45.7 %, 31.3 % and 22.9 % samples tested, respectively.

Conclusions: The determination of the *Blastocystis* ST3 subtype as the most frequently isolated ST in the studied population, is consistent with the literature data. The wide spectrum of animal species that are carriers of the ST3 subtype may suggest zoonotic infections. Molecular studies confirmed high level of contamination of investigated school children with *Blastocystis* that corresponds most probably with poor sanitary conditions.

This study was supported and co-funded by the project of the Military Institute of Medicine in Warsaw (No 573) and by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (MUG ST 02- 0104/772).

Poster 12 (P12)

Disentangling the epidemiology of *Blastocystis* in Nicaragua: preliminary data from a cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Background: The epidemiology of *Blastocystis* in Nicaragua is largely unknown. Molecular-based data are necessary to identify subtypes, which is key to understanding the transmission dynamics of the protist.

Methods: In this cross-sectional survey, individual stool samples from 88 apparently healthy children (median age: 6 years; range: 1-13; male/female ratio: 1.0) residing on a rural Nicaraguan island were collected during January 2023. Initial detection of *Blastocystis* was conducted by PCR. Subtype assignment (including identification of mixed infections) was carried out by next-generation sequencing using Illumina technology.

Results: *Blastocystis* carriage was confirmed in 27.3% (24/88; 95% CI: 18.3–37.8) of the participating children. Sequence analyses identified four known subtypes (ST1, ST2, ST3, and ST7) and a potentially novel subtype. Mono-subtype infections (70.8%; 17/24) were more common than mixed subtype infections (29.2%; 7/24) among *Blastocystis*-positive samples. Mono-infections included ST1 (45.8%, 11/24), ST2 (4.2%, 1/24), and ST3 (20.8%, 5/24). The potentially novel ST was identified in combination with ST2 (12.5%, 3/24) or with ST1+ST2 (4.2%, 1/24). Other coinfections included ST1+ST3 (8.3%, 2/24) and ST3+ST7 (4.2%, 1/24). The dominance of ST1/ST3 coincides with previous data from the Americas region. The finding of avian-adapted ST7 is indicative of a potential avian-human zoonotic transmission event, although lack of prevalence and genotyping data from domestic animals and wildlife precluded us to confirm this hypothesis.

Conclusion: Data indicate that *Blastocystis* is a common finding in Nicaraguan children. More molecular-based studies targeting human, animal, and environmental samples are needed to disentangle the epidemiology of *Blastocystis* in Nicaragua.

Poster 13 (P13)

Evaluation of the diagnostic performance of microscopy, xenic culturing, and next generation sequencing techniques for the detection of *Blastocystis*

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Abstract

Background: Microscopy and xenic culturing remain the first-line diagnostic methods for the detection of *Blastocystis* in many clinical laboratories globally. However, highly sensitive PCR-based methods with high throughput and rapid turnaround times are increasingly replacing conventional methods in a cost-effective manner. This study compares the diagnostic performance of microscopy, xenic culturing, and next-generation sequencing (NGS) for the detection of *Blastocystis* in human stool samples.

Methods: *Blastocystis* sp. was investigated in stool samples from patients ($n = 338$) undergoing colorectal cancer screening in Medellín (Colombia) by direct microscopy examination of concentrated material vs. microscopy of xenic culture in Jones medium vs. PCR plus NGS methods. Statistical analyses were conducted to assess the agreement between tests.

Results: *Blastocystis* was identified by direct microscopy examination and concentrated material in 33.1% (112/338; 95% CI: 28.0–38.3), by microscopy of xenic culture in Jones medium in 33.4% (113/338; 95% CI: 28.3–38.6) and by PCR-NGS in 34.6% (117/338; 95% CI: 29.4–40.0). Kappa indexes of 0.967 (direct microscopy vs. xenic culturing), 0.782 (direct microscopy vs. PCR-NGS), and 0.789 (xenic culturing vs. PCR-NGS) confirmed the concordance of the results obtained with the different techniques compared.

Conclusion: Contrary to what might be expected, direct microscopy examination (either of concentrated material or from xenic cultures) performed equally well than PCR-NGS in the detection of *Blastocystis* in stool samples. Such a striking result highlights the importance of having highly trained and experienced personnel in clinical microbiology laboratories where conventional microscopy cannot be replaced by molecular-based techniques.

Poster 14 (P14)

Frequency and molecular diversity of *Blastocystis* in patients with and without colorectal cancer from Medellín, Colombia

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* is a major colonizer of the human gastrointestinal tract with a global distribution. Prevalences range from 0.5–24% in developed nations to 50–100% in developing countries. Based on sequence analyses of the small subunit ribosomal RNA (*ssu-rRNA*) gene, at least 40 *Blastocystis* subtypes (STs) are currently considered.

Methods: Stool samples ($n = 338$) were collected from patients with a normal colonoscopy (non-CRC group, $n = 184$) and patients with cancer (CRC group, $n = 154$) in five hospitals in Medellín, Colombia. Initial detection of *Blastocystis* sp. was conducted by *ssu-rRNA* PCR and confirmation and ST identification (including mixed infections) by next-generation sequencing (Illumina).

Results: The frequency of *Blastocystis* sp. was 33.7% (62/184) in the non-CRC group and 35.7% (55/154) in the CRC group. A total of 11 different STs were identified. ST3 was the most common ST (59.0%) followed by ST1 (31.6%), ST2 (27.4%), ST4 (10.3%), ST6, ST7, and ST10a (1.7% each), and ST14, ST30, ST41, and ST44 (0.9% each). There were no statistically significant differences between non-CRC and CRC in relation to specific STs. Mixed infections involving different STs were common (24.8%), with 8 cases being infected by 2 different STs, 5 cases with 3 STs, one case with 4 STs and even one case infected by 6 different STs.

Conclusion: *Blastocystis* infection was highly frequent in both non-CRC and CRC groups and the substantial molecular diversity observed was independent of the clinical status.

Poster 15 (P15)

Genetic diversity at the *ssu* rDNA gene does not play a role in the pathogenicity of *Blastocystis* infection in clinical patients

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Abstract

The clinical significance of *Blastocystis* sp. is a question that still needs to be solved. This study assesses whether *Blastocystis* subtype diversity can affect the outcome of the infection and the occurrence of clinical manifestations in infected individuals. Stool samples from 219 *Blastocystis*-positive patients diagnosed by PCR (targeting the *ssu* rDNA gene) were collected from a tertiary public hospital in Madrid (Spain) and fully genotyped by Sanger sequencing analyses. Co-infections by other parasitic, viral, and bacterial enteropathogens were identified by molecular and culture methods. Epidemiological and clinical data from patients was collected. Sequence analyses revealed the presence of six *Blastocystis* subtypes including ST1 (21.5%), ST2 (17.8%), ST3 (29.7%), ST4 (22.8%), ST6 (5.5%), and ST7 (2.3%), with a single sample harbouring a ST1+ST3 co-infection (0.5%). Overall, 81.7% of the patients presented with some gastrointestinal symptom. Multivariate risk factor analyses using logistic regression models indicated that neither *Blastocystis* subtypes nor patient-associated variables including sex, country of origin, travelling history, and presence of nonspecific symptoms were positively associated with a higher likelihood of developing gastrointestinal symptoms (abdominal pain and diarrhoea). However, being of a young age (p -value: 0.003), experiencing skin pruritus (p -value < 0.001) and showing eosinophilia (p -value: 0.016) were found to increase the odds of presenting gastrointestinal symptoms in *Blastocystis* infection. We conclude that the occurrence of gastrointestinal manifestations is independent of the *Blastocystis* subtype involved in the infection, based on variability within the *ssu* rDNA gene.

Poster 16 (P16)

High prevalence of *Blastocystis* in non-human primates from a zoo in Serbia

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* is an anaerobic protozoa with controversial pathogenic significance, registered in gastrointestinal tract of both humans and animals. The infection can be self-limited but some studies have shown that in humans *Blastocystis* is related to inflammatory bowel disease, while in animals to diarrhea, abdominal pain, nausea and gastric distension.

Method: To assess the presence of *Blastocystis* sp. we performed xenic *in vitro* cultivation in modified Jones' medium supplemented with 10% horse serum and molecular analysis identifying a specific region of the small subunit ribosomal RNA (*SSU* rRNA). We collected 17 fecal samples of eight captive non-human primate's species (Barbery macaque, Ring-tailed lemur, Red-bellied lemur, Tufted capucin, Common patas monkey, Chimpanzee, De Brazza's monkey, Common marmoset) in Palić Zoo, located in the north of Serbia. DNA extraction was performed using commercial stool DNA Extrac5on Kit EURx, Poland. *Blastocystis* sp. was determined through PCR amplifica5on of an approximately 600 bp region of the *SSU* rRNA gene using the forward RD5 and reverse BhrDr primers.

Results: Among 17 samples, 6 (35,3%) were positive by xenic *in vitro* cultivation. Molecular analysis showed the high prevalence of *Blastocystis*, 88,2% (15/17) present in different species.

Conclusion: The two diagnostic methods were in line in 8 samples (6 positive and 2 negative), while 9 samples were only PCR positive. The PCR method showed higher sensitivity when compared with cultiva5on and should be encouraged in *Blastocystis* diagnosis. The presence of the potential zoonotic *Blastocystis* subtypes could be possible, hence their transmission between non-human primates and humans.

Poster 17 (P17)

Investigation of *Blastocystis* positivity and subtypes in stool samples from Afyonkarahisar Health Sciences University Faculty of Medicine Microbiology Laboratory

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Abstract

Background: Despite being a common intestinal protozoan in Turkey, studies on *Blastocystis* are limited to certain regions. The main objective of this study is to investigate *Blastocystis* positivity using PCR in samples from a University Faculty of Medicine Microbiology laboratory for routine parasitology examination, and to determine their genotypes.

Methods: The present study included 190 fecal samples and has been supported by Afyon Karahisar Health Sciences University, with ongoing research. Genomic DNA isolation was performed on the samples using a commercial kit, and the barcode region was amplified. The alignment and querying of par5a1 18S rRNA sequences were submitted to the pubmlst.org database. Demographic characteristics of patients were also analyzed.

Results: Among the patients, 48.1% were male, and the majority were under 18 years old. Additionally, it was observed that patients from the city center accounted for the highest proportion of all. *Blastocystis* positivity was found to be 4.2% with PCR, with three subtypes detected: ST3, ST2, and ST1. There was a predominance of samples from pediatric services.

Conclusions: The findings of this project are consistent with others in our country. The forthcoming findings will contribute to a clearer understanding of *Blastocystis* in this region. The low rate of *Blastocystis* in children age group was also needs more attention.

The study was supported by AFSU Scientific Research Commission with project id:23gene1004.

Poster 18 (P18)

Non-symptomatic children harbor *Blastocystis* and *Dientamoeba fragilis* more: Outcomes of a field study from Nepal

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Abstract

Background: *Blastocystis* spp. and *Dientamoeba fragilis* are blamed for infections in humans, while application of PCR indicated high prevalence rates for *Dientamoeba fragilis* (43% in Denmark) and *Blastocystis* (100% in Senegalese children) in healthy individuals, which questions their roles in human health. Here, we present the related outcomes of our stool examinations of children during the field studies in rural Nepal between 2013 and 2015.

Material/methods: Stools of 203 children aged 2-15 years were collected between 2013-2015 in rural Nepal. Routine O&P examination and Kinyoun staining were done for all samples kept and transported in fixative solutions, while *Dientamoeba fragilis* was sought using Real-Time PCR, as described (Verweij et al., 2007). A detailed inquiry form was filled in by the voluntary staff having questions on both personal information and physical examination.

Results: O&P examinations indicated *Blastocystis* in 58 (28.6%) of 203 children. Adequate DNA was extracted from 153 children stools and *D. fragilis* DNA was identified in 110 (71.9%). Other identified intestinal parasites were *Entamoeba histolytica/dispar* (n=38), *Giardia lamblia* (n=34) *Cryptosporidium* spp. (n=24), *Cyclospora cayetanensis* (n=14) and *Hymenolepis nana* (n=3). It was noted that *D. fragilis* and *Blastocystis*-positive children were predominantly non-symptomatic.

Conclusions: Children in developing countries are under the threat of parasitic diseases that may disturb their physical and mental development. Therefore, public health measures are required to improve infrastructure and life standards of citizens. Both *D. fragilis* and *Blastocystis*-positive children were mostly non-symptomatic during the study; this may contribute to the discussions on their roles in human health.

Poster 19 (P19)

Occurrence of *Blastocystis* subtype ST1 in primates in ZOO Košice, Slovakia

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Abstract

Blastocystis sp. poses a public health problem due to its global distribution among many animal hosts, including humans. This study aimed to investigate the subtype diversity of *Blastocystis* spp. in the Košice ZOO. Fecal samples were collected from 23 animals (5 brown bears, 2 pandas, 7 leopards, 2 lemurs, and 7 primates) showing no clinical symptoms. In addition to conventional parasitological examination using the flotation method, molecular characterization of *Blastocystis* sp. was conducted using PCR method. DNA amplification was carried out using the small subunit ribosomal RNA gene (18S rRNA gene) and forward and reverse primers (RD5/BhRDr).

Overall, *Blastocystis* sp. was detected in only 2 primates out of 23 samples. Sanger sequencing analysis revealed 100 % similarity with subtype ST1. Furthermore, co-infection with *Trichuris* spp. was confirmed in these two primates using the flotation method.

Primates serve as significant hosts for *Blastocystis* sp., indicating the importance of screening measures. Given the potential for direct contact between zoo personnel, veterinarians, and zoo visitors, there is an increased risk of *Blastocystis* sp. transmission. Therefore, regular screening of primates in captive settings is recommended to mitigate transmission risks.

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Paper 20 (P20)

Occurrence of *Blastocystis* sp. in a gut-healthy human population and their animals in the Czech Republic and its impact on the gut microbiota

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Abstract

Blastocystis sp. is a widespread intestinal protist and its prevalence in humans varies between low- and high-income countries. Its role in the human gut ecosystem is still unclear as knowledge about its epidemiology and the factors influencing intestinal colonization is incomplete. To date, very few studies have addressed the question of whether there is a link between the incidence of *Blastocystis* in humans in high-income countries and contact with pets and farm animals. In this study, we also focused on zoonotic potential of *Blastocystis* and whether its presence and other factors have an impact on the composition of the gut microbiota.

This study provides data on the prevalence and subtype diversity of *Blastocystis* sp. in a gut-healthy human population and in their pet or farm animals. A total of 288 stool samples were obtained from asymptomatic individuals across the wide age-range and 136 samples from animals. *Blastocystis* was detected by PCR and its subtypes determined based on the obtained sequences and phylogenetic analyzes. In humans, the prevalence was 24% and eight subtypes were found; in animals, the prevalence was 10%, and only five subtypes were detected. A higher incidence of *Blastocystis* was observed in people with frequent contact with farm animals and in travelers outside Europe. We also analyzed the microbial diversity of selected samples. Our results show that living in a village and the presence or absence of *Blastocystis* has an impact on the composition of the gut microbiota.

Poster 21 (P21)

Presence of *Blastocystis* in pre-washed vegetables from a supermarket in South East England

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Abstract

Blastocystis is a widespread protist which colonises the gut of various species including humans, wildlife, livestock, and companion animals. In humans it is the most prevalent eukaryotic microbe of the gastrointestinal tract and has been found in individuals with symptomatic and asymptomatic infections. *Blastocystis* has been shown to contaminate various leafy vegetables that are destined for human consumption worldwide, however studies assessing the presence of this organism in pre-washed and ready-to-eat vegetables (RTE) are limited. Our study aim was to assess the presence of *Blastocystis* contamination in RTE from different supermarkets in the UK. Between May 2023 and July 2023, a total of 36 RTE were purchased from four major supermarkets in Canterbury, UK. Following DNA extraction, 24 out of the 36 samples had sufficient DNA. These samples underwent nested PCR to amplify the *Blastocystis* small subunit (SSU) rRNA gene sequence and gel extraction of the amplified products was subsequently carried out and sent for Sanger sequencing. Twenty one percent (5/24) of the RTE samples were PCR-positive and sequence positive for *Blastocystis*. Two of the positive samples were identified to be subtype (ST) 1 and three were identified as ST2. None of the samples were positive for both subtypes. All positive samples originated from one supermarket. This study underscores the importance of RTE vegetables as a potential vehicle for *Blastocystis* transmission to humans, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to identify contamination sources and develop effective prevention strategies.

Poster 22 (P22)

Prevalence of intestinal parasites with a focus on molecular identification of *Giardia duodenalis*, *Blastocystis* sp., and *Cryptosporidium* spp. in children hospitalised at the Children's Faculty Hospital in Košice

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Abstract

Intestinal parasitic infections are prevalent worldwide and have been identified as one of the most significant causes of diseases in human populations, particularly in children. Several studies concerning the detection of intestinal protozoa and helminths in the human population have been conducted in Slovakia; however, no survey of the occurrence of *Blastocystis* sp. in humans has been carried out so far.

The present research focused mainly on the detection of *Blastocystis* sp., as well as other protozoan species *Giardia duodenalis* and *Cryptosporidium* spp. in children hospitalised at the Children's Faculty Hospital in Košice. A total of 76 faecal samples were collected from symptomatic and asymptomatic children. Detection of *Blastocystis* sp. was performed using PCR with the *SSU* rRNA gene and RD5/BhRDr primers with negative results so far. The samples were examined for the presence of *Giardia* cysts using the flotation method, while the molecular detection of *G. duodenalis* was carried out with the use of the *bg*, *tpi*, *gdh* genes. Out of 14 samples, 7 were identified as assemblage A and 5 as assemblage B; mixed assemblages (A, F) and (B, F) were also identified. The ELISA test was used for proof of the coproantigen in the detection of *Cryptosporidium* spp. from faecal specimens, with negative results (VEGA No. 1/0709/23 and APVV-19-0493).

Our preliminary results indicate a higher prevalence of *G. duodenalis* in the studied population of children compared to other protozoan species. As the study is still ongoing, possible occurrence of *Cryptosporidium* spp. and *Blastocystis* sp. cannot be ruled out.

Poster 23 (P23)

Primer spacers (staggering) improve the performance of *Blastocystis* subtyping using the massively parallel amplicon sequencing of the informative 18S rDNA region

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Abstract

The subtypes of *Blastocystis* can be efficiently determined using massively parallel amplicon sequencing as specified by Maloney et al [Infect Genet Evol. 2019;73:119-25], i.e. with primers originally developed by Santin et al [Parasitol Res. 2011;109:205-12] extended with Illumina Nextera tails. However, the amplicons exhibit high similarity at numerous locations. This homogeneity presents a challenge to the acquisition of signal on the Illumina MiSeq platform that fails to provide quality sequencing signal unless a very large concentration of the *PhiX* heterogeneity library is added.

A systematic, algorithm-driven approach was therefore employed to design heterogeneity spacers for primers. These were tested *in silico* and *in vitro* in marker gene profiling applications, including *Blastocystis* subtyping. We aimed to design a primer set that would produce no more than 60% dominant base in any sequencing cycle.

Additional bases (spacers) were inserted into the first-round amplification primer construct between the binding site of the Illumina sequencing primer and the target-specific portion. The aforementioned primers were then used similarly to their non-staggered counterparts. Of note, the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was conducted as a single multiplexed reaction per sample. A simple script was used to remove the heterogeneity spacers from the reads, and to verify that the primer combinations were equally represented. A total of sixteen staggered primer variants were designed for bi-directional amplicon profiling of the 18S rDNA region informative for *Blastocystis* subtypes. The efficacy of our design can be evidenced by an increase in the heterogeneity of the sequencing signal, and the increase in the effective sequencing capacity.

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Poster 24 (P24)

The link between parasitic infection *Blastocystis hominis* and *Helicobacter pylori*: A descriptive study

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Abstract

Background: Some researchers have reported the attendant link between parasitic infections including *Blastocystis hominis* (*B. hominis*) and *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection. The study aimed to evaluate the frequency of intestinal parasites (*B. hominis* and *H. pylori*) and associated clinical symptoms in human faecal samples.

Methods: This cross-sectional study occurred during the periods January 2023 to March 2024. Approximately 258 adult faecal samples with gastrointestinal concerns, for more than 6 months were examined in the parasitology laboratory for parasites (with Formalin-ether sedimentation by microscopy) and *H. pylori* (Stool Antigen Test).

Results: Patients belong to both sexes, ranging in age from 25 to 75 years. Parasitic infection was found in 33.7% of patients, with *Giardia lamblia* and *B. hominis* being the most often discovered species in 19.8% (51/258) and 5.8% (15/258), respectively. Among *H. pylori* positives, 23.1% (31/134) had a co-infection, and *B. hominis*-*H. pylori* was the most common coinfection followed by *G. lamblia*-*H. pylori*. Based on the clinical complaints of patients, the positive rate for *H. pylori* was 51.9% (134/258). Clinical complaints were associated with the disease (p-value < 0.05), where irritable bowel syndrome (25.2%) and gastric reflux resulted as the most common complaints followed by abdominal discomfort (19.37%), diarrhea (8.5%), anorexia (3.1%) and nausea (2.7%).

Conclusion: Our data showed a link between *H. pylori* and *B. hominis*. Given that the evidence is still uncertain as to how *H. pylori* promote intestinal parasitosis or inversely, caution should be exercised when we screen the faeces for parasitic diseases. More research is needed, specifically to determine the link with intestinal microbial ecosystems.

Poster 25 (P25)

Zoonotic intestinal protists: A cross-sectional survey of non-human primates and caregivers in Zoos

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Abstract

We investigated the prevalence, genetic diversity and potential zoonotic transmission of two intestinal protists - *Blastocystis* sp. and *Giardia intestinalis* - in 37 species of non-human primates (NHPs) and their caregivers in six zoos in the Czech Republic. We analyzed 179 fecal samples (159 from NHPs, 20 from humans) by qPCR. The overall prevalence of *Blastocystis* sp. detected using qPCR in caregivers was 35% (7/20) and in the NHP hosts 57% (91/159). The prevalence of *Giardia intestinalis* was 30% (6/20) in caregivers and 47% in the NHP hosts (74/159). Using next generation sequencing we identified a range of *Blastocystis* subtypes (ST1-ST5, ST7, ST8) of which some were shared between NHPs and their caregivers, suggesting possible zoonotic transmission. In the case of *Giardia*, we found assemblages A and B. Our study emphasizes the critical role of molecular diagnostics and calls for further research on the epidemiology and transmission of these protists to better understand their public health impact.

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